

THERMOMECHANICAL BEHAVIOR OF SQUEEZE CAST SIC/AL METAL-MATRIX COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY: Aluminum-matrix composites containing thermally oxidized SiC particles of controlled diameter ranging from 3 to 40 μm were successfully produced by vacuum assisted- high pressure infiltration. Their thermal expansion coefficients were measured between 25 and 500°C, and compared with the predictions of various theoretical models. The thermal expansion behavior of three-phase Al-SiC-SiO₂ composite show no significant deviation from the predictions of elastic analysis, since the measured CTEs lie within the elastic bounds derived by Schapery's analysis. The effect of particle size is quite evident in the pressure infiltrated composites reinforced with oxidized ceramic particulates. The larger the particles, the greater the thermal expansion of the composite. The observed behavior of these composites is discussed in terms of particle size, silica layer formed during oxidation, and thermal stresses developed as a result of the difference in the coefficient of thermal expansion between the reinforcement and the matrix.

KEYWORDS: metal-matrix, SiC particle, oxidation, squeeze casting, thermal expansion

INTRODUCTION

Advanced composites show considerable promise for applications where weight and volume are critical as, for example, in aircraft and space vehicles. Aluminum alloys reinforced with various ceramics such as SiC and Al₂O₃ (MMC) are gaining commercial importance. Although these composites are quite light they exhibit significant improvements in strength and elastic modulus [1-3], wear resistance [4], fatigue resistance [5] and damping capacity [6] in addition to high-temperature mechanical properties [7] and low thermal expansion [8].

The coefficient of thermal expansion of metal-matrix composites can be tailored by varying the nature, volume fraction and morphology of the reinforcement in the composite. A low CTE and high thermal conductivity are desirable for applications such as electronic heat sinks and space structures. Furthermore, a low density is desirable for aerospace applications, particularly electrical structural applications. Conventional metals for electronic packaging applications include Cu, Al, Ni-Fe alloys, and Cu-W and Cu-Mo blends; however, these materials do not meet the requirements in advanced electronic packaging applications for low CTE, high thermal conductivity, low density and low cost.

The limitations of conventional metallic materials have led to increased focus on SiC particle reinforced Aluminum-matrix composites as potential candidates for a variety of uses in

advanced electronic packaging. The SiC particulates, which are available in different structures from inexpensive raw material sources, exhibit low density ($d=3.2 \text{ g/cm}^3$), low CTE ($\alpha=4.7 \times 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$), high Young's modulus ($E=450 \text{ GPa}$), and a commercially available particle size range of 1 to 80 μm . The thermal conductivity, κ , of SiC is in the range 80 to 200 $\text{W}/(\text{m}\cdot\text{K})$, depending on purity and processing conditions. By contrast, pure Al has the following physical properties : $d=2.7 \text{ g/cm}^3$, $E=70 \text{ GPa}$, $\alpha=23 \times 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$, and $\kappa=180$ to 230 $\text{W}/(\text{m}\cdot\text{K})$.

The present investigation was undertaken with the objective of studying the thermal expansion behavior of isotropic metal-matrix composites reinforced with SiC particles. In this work, composites having a matrix of high purity aluminum containing oxidized SiC reinforcements ranging from 3 to 40 μm in size were successfully produced using the high pressure infiltration technique. The coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) of the MMCs was measured between 25 and 500°C, and compared to the predictions of three theoretical models.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

Metal-Matrix Composites Production by Squeeze Casting

The composites were fabricated by vacuum-assisted infiltration of a liquid metal into a porous preform under high pressure. The matrix was 99.9 pct initial purity aluminum from ALCOA™ (Trademark, Aluminum Company of America, Pittsburgh, PA, USA). Four SiC particulates from two suppliers with average diameters in the range 3 to 40 μm were used. Thickness of preform used in this study was 30 mm. The procedure of preform fabrication can be outlined as follows. First, SiC particles were packed by hand into a boat made of Fiberfrax™ board. Stirring by impeller was performed to establish a uniform particle distribution. Finally, oxidation of particles in air under programmed heating and isothermal conditions was carried out at 1300°C. The temperature in the hot zone was kept constant to within $\pm 1^\circ\text{C}$. As the preforms used in this study were fabricated with different particle sizes, the oxidation time was varied somewhat, ranging from two to four hours. Preforms were infiltrated with pure aluminum using the squeeze casting press shown in Fig.1.

The composite samples were cut along their length on a low-speed diamond saw with ethanol as a lubricant. Metallography was performed on the Al/SiC composites by grinding the samples with a 200 grit perforated diamond wheel. Samples were then polished using 15 μm , 6 μm and 3 μm Buehler Metadi™ (Lake Bluff, IL, USA) diamond suspension on a Buehler Metlap 10™ spiral polishing platens. Samples were washed with water and ethanol between polishing steps. Finally, samples were polished for approximately 10 minutes on Buehler Chemomet™ polishing cloth using Buehler Mastermet™ polishing compound. Scanning electron microscope examination of the polished composite was performed on a Jeol 840 microscope equipped with EDAX energy dispersive X-Ray analysis. The volume fractions of the SiC particles were measured using an IBAS2 image analyzer system attached to an optical microscope.

Fig. 1: Schematic of the pressure infiltration unit.

Measurement of Thermal Expansion

Specimens for CTE testing, 10 x 5 x 2 mm in size, were machined from the prepared MMC samples. Specimen surfaces were polished using 1 μm diamond paste. More than four samples of each composite were tested under each condition to verify reproducibility of the data. CTE measurements were performed from 25°C to 500°C at 5°C/min using a commercial thermal mechanical analysis equipment (model TMA 2940, Dupont, USA). The thicknesses of the samples were measured with increased sensitivity (0.1 μm) using the standard expansion probe. The data were obtained in the form of PLC (per cent linear change) versus temperature curve. TMA standard data analysis software was used to evaluate the coefficient of thermal expansion of the composites tested.

RESULTS

Composite Characterization

Fig. 2 shows SEM micrograph of polished section of the SiC/Al composite. Pressure infiltration of the oxidized preforms produced composites in which most of the material appeared to be free of porosity and microscopically homogeneous and thus, are expected to have isotropic properties. The SEM micrographs for the oxidized SiC particles, as compared to those of unoxidized particulates, showed that the SiC particles have been cemented together by the viscous silica glass formed by the oxidation reaction. The large reinforcements (20-40 μm) exhibited less coalescence than the other materials. The silicon carbide particulates showed extensive coarsening following this oxidation exposure and clear evidence of bonding of the particles by the glassy silica phase. After oxidation at 1300°C, even for periods of 2 hrs, the small particles of 3 μm in size were found to have fused into a bonded network as a result of the flow of the silica glass from particle to particle.

The volume fraction of silicon carbide in the composites was determined via image analysis. The average volume fraction of oxidized particles was 56 vol.%, regardless the size of ceramic particulate.

Fig. 2: Typical Microstructure of infiltrated SiC/Al metal-matrix composite.

Thermal Expansion

The results of the thermal expansion (expressed as a PLC), as a function of temperature, for the different composites, containing oxidized SiC particulates, are shown in Fig. 3. In general, the thermal cycling experiments produced no conclusive evidence of thermal ratcheting in any of the materials during two cycles. As shown in Fig.3, the effect of particle size is quite evident and the larger the particles, the greater is the thermal expansion at a particular temperature.

Fig. 3: Per cent linear change (PLC) versus temperature for composites reinforced with various oxidized SiC particle sizes: (a) 3 μm, (b) 10 μm, (c) 20 μm, and (d) 40 μm.

Fig. 4 shows the values of the coefficient of thermal expansion as a function of temperature for each of the composites tested. Note that the CTE is determined at intervals of 50°C based on the calculated slope fit between two selected temperatures. As expected from Fig.3, the larger oxidized particle reinforced composite shows consistently higher CTE than the composite containing smaller oxidized particles. It is evident for a given composite, that the CTE is decreased by the oxidation process. This is consistent with image analysis results which indicate a higher volume fraction of the composite reinforcement in the case of oxidized particles.

DISCUSSION

Theoretical Models

Several theoretical analyses have been presented in the literature which give expressions for the CTE of the metal-matrix composite; these are reviewed in Refs. [9,10]. Of these, the simplest and most used are those of Kerner, Schapery and Turner.

Kerner's Model

The Kerner model assumes that the reinforcement is spherical and wetted by a uniform layer of matrix; thus the CTE of the composite is stated to be identical with that of a volume element composed of a spherical reinforcement particle surrounded by a shell of matrix, both phases having the volume fractions present in the composite. This model gives the composite CTE as:

$$\alpha_c = \bar{\alpha} + V_p(1 - V_p)(\alpha_p - \alpha_m) \frac{K_p - K_m}{(1 - V_p)K_m + V_p K_p + (3K_p K_m / 4G_m)} \quad (1)$$

Where the rule of mixture is given by $\bar{\alpha} = (1 - V_p)\alpha_m + V_p \alpha_p$. K and G are the bulk and shear moduli, V is the volume fraction, and α is the coefficient of thermal expansion. The bulk modulus is calculated using the standard relationship :

$$K = \frac{E}{3(3 - E/G)} \quad (2)$$

b) Schapery's Model

Among the several formulae that have been suggested for the calculation of the thermal expansion coefficient of composite materials taking into account the stress interaction between components is that of Schapery who has derived the effective CTE of isotropic composites. By employing extremum principles of thermoelasticity, The CTE value can be written as

$$\alpha_c = \alpha_p + (\alpha_m - \alpha_p) \frac{(1/K_c) - (1/K_p)}{(1/K_m) - (1/K_p)} \quad (3)$$

Where α_c and K_c are the CTE and bulk modulus of the composite. Note that α_c depends on the volume fraction and phase geometry only through their effect on bulk modulus. This

equation provides an exact relation between composite CTE and bulk modulus. However, only upper and lower bounds of K_c are known in a given case (Hashin's bounds [11]), thus, this expression will provide only bounds on CTE. The lower bound on bulk modulus is

$$K_c^{(-)} = K_m + \frac{V_p}{\frac{1}{K_p - K_m} + \frac{V_m}{K_m + \frac{4}{3}G_m}} \quad (4)$$

The upper bound is obtained by interchanging indices m and p everywhere. Lower bound on K_c yields the upper bound on the composite CTE shown in equation (1) (and vice-versa). It is noteworthy that this upper bound of composite CTE was shown by Schapery to coincide with CTE value determined using Kerner's model. This is not surprising since Hashin's lower bound for bulk modulus is stated to be an exact result for elastic composite, in which the reinforcement is a sphere coated with a uniform layer of the matrix.

c) Turner's Model

The Turner model considered that an internal stress system on a mixture containing n phases is such that the stresses are nowhere sufficient to disrupt the composite, the sum of the internal forces can be equated to zero and an expression of the CTE of the composite is obtained.

$$\alpha_c = \frac{\sum_i^n \alpha_i V_i K_i}{\sum_i^n V_i K_i} \quad (5)$$

Where V is the volume fraction.

It is interesting to point out, none of the many models that have been proposed for calculating the CTE of a composite incorporates a dependence on particle size. Nevertheless, we have used the Turner, Schapery and Kerner expressions to see whether any of them fitted our results.

Theoretical Calculations of Three-phase Al-SiC-SiO₂ Composite CTE

The apparent influence of reinforcement particle size on the CTE may reflect differences in the relative amount of silicon oxide formed as particle size varies: with a roughly constant silica layer thickness, smaller particles feature more silica in proportion to SiC. To evaluate the influence of this effect, the CTE of composites of aluminum reinforced with silica-coated SiC was evaluated under the assumption that the reinforcement is spherical and coated with a uniform thickness of silica. So, considering V_p uncoated particles volume fraction, the number of particles, N, is $N = 6V_p / \pi d^3$, where d is the SiC particle size. The volume fraction of silica layer for thickness t is:

$$V_{SiO_2} = N \left[\frac{\pi}{6} (d + 2t)^3 - \frac{\pi}{6} (d)^3 \right] \quad (6)$$

and then we calculate the CTE change expected for different size particles and different thickness interface layer. The reinforcement CTE and bulk modulus were calculated for each particle size explored in this work, using the Kerner model, use of which is justified by the predominantly convex shape of the SiC reinforcement. Using these values for the reinforcement properties, elastic bounds for aluminum reinforced with silica-coated SiC were then calculated using Kerner's and Schapery's formulae (Eq. (1) and (3)). Finally, Turner's model was used to determine the CTE of three-phase Al-SiC-SiO₂ composite.

Numerical values of parameters used for the computation of predicted composite CTE using Eqs. (1), (2) and (4) are extracted from previous work [12,13]. The variation in Young's and shear moduli with temperature for pure aluminum was examined using Dynamic Mechanical Analysis (DMA), and a summary of the elastic constants evaluated is provided in Table 1.

Table 1: Properties of SiC, SiO₂ and pure Al.

T°C	SiC			SiO ₂			Pure Aluminum		
	E (GPa)	G (GPa)	CTE (μ/°C)	E (GPa)	G (GPa)	CTE (μ/°C)	E (GPa)	G (GPa)	CTE (μ/°C)
50	450	192	4.5	70.5	30.7	0.41	72.03	27.2	21.8
100	450	192	4.5	71.3	31.1	0.47	70.66	26.6	22.4
200	450	192	4.5	72.3	31.6	0.55	65.90	24.7	23.9
300	450	192	4.5	73.4	32.1	0.58	63.73	24.1	25.9
400	450	192	4.5	74.2	32.5	0.61	49.16	18.1	27.8
500	450	192	4.5	75.2	33.5	0.62	36.91	13.2	29.5

Comparison Between the Experimental and Theoretical Results

The comparison between the theoretical calculations and experimental results for the composites produced with preform oxidation is shown in Fig. 4. In the case of composites which contain larger oxidized particles (20 and 40 μm), the experimental CTEs agree well with the values predicted by the Schapery model at low temperatures (50-150°C), while the CTEs in 400-500°C temperature range, are relatively close to Kerner's predictions. On the 200-400°C range, the experimental CTEs show a rapid increase, and do not agree with any of the theories and this underlines the influence of matrix plasticity. On the other hand, CTE values measured on composites produced from oxidized preforms show no significant deviation from the predictions of elastic analysis, since these lie within the elastic bounds derived by Schapery's analysis. This feature was reported in previous work [14] on Duralcan Al₂O₃/6061 composites containing high volume fraction of reinforcement (40%). A good agreement with Kerner's model at high temperatures was found while the CTEs in the low-temperatures agreed relatively well with the values predicted by Schapery's equation.

The results in terms of particle size effect, indicate that the oxidized particles interact sufficiently strongly with the surrounding aluminum that they are able to modify the thermal expansion behavior of the bulk material. The greater the particle size, the higher is the thermal expansion. The more constraint in the composites reinforced with smaller oxidized

particulates is attributed to the interfacial zone where a layer of silica exists because of oxidation. Since the interfacial area is related to the particle size, the volume of the interfacial zone will depend on the particle size and accordingly, the CTE of the composites will vary with the reinforcement size. It is not surprising that very small particles, with their larger surface area, have a greater effect than large particles—as our own observations demonstrate. The measured CTE shows, for each composite type, similar variations with temperature, but with a slight decrease in the CTE value by about $10^{-6} \text{ }^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$, as the SiC particle size decreases from 40 to 3 μm . This effect of particle size is, as shown in Fig. 4, relatively well predicted by mechanical models using three phases composite system.

Recently, Ma et al. [15] have examined the effect of reinforcement size on the CTE of SiC/Al metal-matrix composite, in which the SiC particle sizes were 3.5, 10 and 20 μm . They reported no significant effect of particle size on the thermal behavior of the composites produced with SiC particles having undergone no oxidation treatment prior to the infiltration process.

Fig. 4: Comparison of the measured CTE of infiltrated SiC/Al composites with the theoretical predictions.

The agreement of the high temperature CTE with the Kerner model prediction is not in agreement with published CTE values for highly loaded SiC particle reinforced aluminum composites, which have been found to agree with the Turner model above 40 vol% SiC [16]. However, Balch et al. [12], in 53 vol% SiC/Al composites produced by pressure infiltration, reported that the measured low-temperature CTE agreed fairly well with that predicted by the Turner model, while the CTE in the high temperature (175–325 $^\circ\text{C}$) were in a good agreement with the Kerner prediction. The authors interpreted these observations as being an effect of residual stresses and void volume change in the thermally cycled composites.

CONCLUSIONS

Several important conclusions can be drawn from this work :

1. Vacuum assisted-high pressure infiltration produced composites in which most of the material appeared to be free of porosity and of high quality.
2. The thermal expansion coefficients of pressure infiltrated metal-matrix composites lie within the elastic bounds derived by Schapery's analysis.
3. Oxidized SiC particles in the amount of 56 vol% decreased the CTE of aluminum from $25.2 \times 10^{-6} \text{ C}^{-1}$ to $12 \times 10^{-6} \text{ C}^{-1}$. In the case of composites which contain larger oxidized particles (20, 40 μm), the experimental CTEs agree well with the values predicted by the Schapery model at low temperatures (50-150°C), while the CTEs in 400-500°C temperature range, are relatively in agreement with Kerner's predictions.
4. The effect of particle size is quite evident and the larger the particles, the greater the thermal expansion of the composite.

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